

Factors that Limit Women Entrepreneur 's Innovation in Egypt

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Abstract

Purpose: This research explores the main reasons why many women entrepreneurs in Egypt struggle to innovate. It looks at both internal challenges like low self-confidence and family responsibilities and external ones, such as limited access to funding, networks, and social support.

Design/methodology/approach: The study uses a qualitative approach by conducting semi-structured interviews with 11 female entrepreneurs from various industries in Egypt. The goal is to understand their experiences and what holds them back from being more innovative in their businesses.

Findings/results: The results show that both internal and external challenges combine to limit innovation. Factors such as fear of failure, emotional pressure, family duties, gender discrimination, financial struggles, and limited networks all play a role. Despite these barriers, many women still find creative ways to adapt and push their businesses forward.

Research implications: This research highlights the need for stronger support systems whether through better access to funding, more awareness about the challenges, or targeted programs that help women balance work and personal responsibilities. Supporting female entrepreneurs can unlock more innovation and lead to stronger economic contributions.

Originality/value: While many studies discuss women in business, few focus specifically on innovation challenges in Egypt. This study provides local insights into real struggles and offers recommendations that match the Egyptian context.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurs, innovation, Egypt, challenges, support, gender barriers

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1. Introduction

Overview

Women's entrepreneurship is a quickly growing global trend that has recently attracted a lot of research and policy interest because of its innovative potential for promoting social and economic progress (Cardella et al., 2020). In order to encourage economic expansion, creativity, and improvements in society, women entrepreneurs are necessary. But in Egypt, historical and societal barriers often result in the opportunity being unused. The challenges which range from monetary limitations to cultural expectations, highlight the importance of an in depth study of the factors limiting the capacity of female entrepreneurs to innovate. One of the most important problems is still access to financing. Unfair loan procedures and a lack of security prevent many female entrepreneurs from accessing formal finance choices, which restricts their capacity to expand or make investments in creative projects (Khalid et al., 2022). This issue is not limited to Egypt, women led businesses worldwide frequently face difficulties obtaining the funding they need to succeed (Cabrera & Mauricio, 2017). The entrepreneurial environment for women is greatly influenced by sociocultural norms in addition to financial limitations. Time and resources are seriously restricted in Egypt due to traditional gender norms which often place a higher priority on women's household tasks than on their professional efforts (Elkafrawi & Refai, 2022). Limited access to professional networks and mentorship, which are essential for promoting innovation and creating long-lasting enterprises, increases these cultural limits even more (Naguib, 2022). Another level of problems is introduced by institutional barriers, such as ineffective management and a lack of gender neutral regulations. Managing regulatory procedures, which do not seek to deal with their specific difficulties, is frequently more challenging for women (Rivera et al., 2024). Additionally, the lack of focused government programs to assist female entrepreneurs makes these problems worse and puts women at a disadvantage in society (Khalid et al., 2022). These linked obstacles show the importance of a variety of approaches to solve the difficulties Egyptian women entrepreneurs face. For women-led innovation to reach its full potential, supportive institutional frameworks, focused education initiatives, cultural changes, and financial inclusion are necessary. The purpose of this study is to expand on exploring the topic by identifying the main barriers to innovation. Understanding the obstacles that prevent women from adopting innovative entrepreneurship is important for a number of reasons. First, economic expansion and corporate success depend on innovation. Women-led businesses have shown the ability to foster diverse marketplaces and promote sustainable development if they receive the necessary support (Cakir

et al., 2024). The lack of institutional support, societal expectations, and financial limitations, however, keep limiting women's ability to innovate and advance in Egypt.

In conclusion, it is essential to understand the barriers to women's entrepreneurial innovation in Egypt in order to promote sustainable growth and economic development. In order to help women entrepreneurs and unlock their potential for innovation and success, this research aims to explain these issues and offer useful information to organizations, companies, and law makers. For Egypt to have a more active and fair entrepreneurship ecosystem, so these obstacles must be removed

Importance of the study

This study is important because it addresses the barriers that keep Egyptian women entrepreneurs from achieving their full abilities when it comes to innovation, which is an essential element of economic growth and competitiveness. In this sense, women entrepreneurs are a poorly used resource, their efforts are consistently ignored due to institutional, cultural, and educational barriers (Cabrera & Mauricio, 2017). Innovation is essential to promoting sustainable development and is not simply a competitive advantage for businesses. Egypt's female entrepreneurs face a number of related problems, such as insufficient education, limiting social standards, and restricted financial access. For example, research indicates that while financial restrictions are a worldwide problem, sociocultural barriers that limit women's independence increase in Egypt (Elkafrawi & Refai, 2022; Naguib, 2022). This study aims to solve these problems and offer policymakers as well as stakeholder's useful information. Women's capacity for innovation can be significantly improved by gender-appropriate financing regulations and better entrepreneurship education. Furthermore, establishing open networks and mentorship programs help close current gaps and produce a fairer entrepreneurial ecosystem (Elkafrawi & Refai, 2022; Bui et al., 2018). The importance of specific to the situation solutions for emerging countries is highlighted by these findings, which add to the global discussion on entrepreneurship and gender equality.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to explore the challenges facing women. to innovation faced by Egyptian women entrepreneurs. The study aims to find out how these obstacles interact to hinder innovation and entrepreneurial success through looking at both internal and external challenges. It will concentrate on understanding the function of both internal and external

factors, including networking opportunities, financial access, and sociocultural norms, as well as human characteristics like emotional intelligence and risk-taking. Finding solutions to these constraints and empowering Egyptian women entrepreneurs to reach their maximum creative potential is the primary goal.

Organization of the paper

This paper is divided into several sections. The study's goals, importance, and research topic are all described in the introduction. With a focus on issues unique to Egypt and similar situations, the Literature Review summarizes the body of research on women's innovation and entrepreneurship. The Methodology describes the research design, data collection methods, and analytical framework. The discussion and findings focus the obstacles found and how they affect Egyptian women entrepreneurs. The Conclusion summarizes the study's findings and highlights its importance of focused efforts, while the Recommendations and Policy Implications offer solutions to address these issues.

2. Literature review

2.1 Women's entrepreneurs overview

Women's entrepreneurship is the term used to describe the role of women who launch, own, and run their own companies, taking on financial risks in order to turn a profit and expand their company. Despite simply becoming financially independent, women's entrepreneurship allows them to promote social change, support in the development of their communities, and serve as an example for other women entrepreneurs.

2.1.1. Characteristics of female entrepreneurs

Since most of study on entrepreneurial personality is conducted at the individual level, there aren't many studies that concentrate on the entrepreneurial level. In addition to being important for starting a firm (Dai et al., 2019), personality traits have attracted the attention of economists, psychologists, sociologists, and business managers who want to know what makes an entrepreneur successful (Kerr et al., 2018). Age and education have a big impact on how

innovative female entrepreneurs are. Women over 40 show higher levels of creativity, relying on their life experiences to generate fresh concepts. To overcome challenges and expand their firms, female entrepreneurs benefit from higher education by gaining knowledge and problem-solving abilities (Rivera et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2021). Success also requires qualities like passion, dedication, and risk tolerance, as proven by a Thai company owner running a successful restaurant. (Putthiwanit & Taeporamaysamai, 2024). But characteristics like age, education, and experience are not enough on their own. For entrepreneurial mindset values, attitudes, and character traits makes a big difference, they need to connect with outside elements like networks and institutional support (Krafft & Rizk, 2021). In the absence of these, experience and education produce little creativity (Rivera et al., 2024).

In conclusion, both entrepreneurship and innovation are supported by an entrepreneurial mindset, which combines individual values, attitudes, and external networks.

2.1.2. Egyptian women's entrepreneurial status

One of the factors affecting the level of women's entrepreneurial activity in Egypt is the low rate of female employment participation, which keeps them from gaining the skills and knowledge required to start and manage a business. (Hassan, 2018). In Egypt, two-thirds of all enterprises are founded by men, making the percentage of women who launch businesses among the lowest in the world. (Bastian & Zali, 2016). In order to empower women and increase their financial stability, female business must grow. It is assumed that women's SMEs improve their financial situation and increase their chances of launching and running their own businesses (Khalid, et al., 2020).

The International Labour Organisation claims that women's involvement and participation in the entrepreneurial sector are a major factor in the huge increase in women's economic empowerment and labour force participation in Egypt. (El-Fiky, 2022). Between 2020 and 2021, Egypt's female/male TEA (total early-stage entrepreneurship) ratio increased from 0.3 to 0.45. The percentage of the economy's adult female population trying to start a new business is generally indicated by the Female/Male TEA (total early-stage entrepreneurship) ratio. This is particularly calculated by dividing the percentage of women in an economy between the ages of 18 and 64 who are either owner-managers of a new business (within the first 42 months after starting one) or new business owners (actively developing a new firm) by the percentage of

men in the economy in the same age group. (GEM,2021). Egyptian women still face several obstacles when it comes to business, even with these encouraging changes. Key barriers that limit their ability to launch and maintain firms are highlighted by studies, such as restricted access to financing, work-family conflicts, and social pressures such gender discrimination (Borham et al., 2024). Family support particularly from spouses is also essential in overcoming these obstacles, although official support networks are still insufficient. The absence of focused managerial skills training, which is necessary for women entrepreneurs to succeed, suggests that stronger institutional support is required, such as funding programs and policy interventions that give priority to female entrepreneurship (Borham et al., 2024 ; Ajonbadi et al., 2024).

2.2. Entrepreneurial innovation overview

Entrepreneurial innovation is the process by which business owners provide fresh ideas, goods, or services to satisfy consumer demands and add value. Innovation of this kind improves industries and pushes growth by promoting economic growth and increasing corporate competitiveness. In addition to helping individual companies, entrepreneurial innovation also encourages more significant change throughout industries, whether through the introduction of new goods or the improvement of current operations.

2.2.1. Definition of innovation

Innovation is the introduction of new concepts, procedures, or goods that add value or expand existing knowledge (Glaeser & Lang, 2023). Service innovation is the process of creating or improving services for the benefit of businesses, consumers, and society. It leads to improved features and novel delivery methods. Good service innovation promotes competitive advantage, productivity, and customer satisfaction while promoting economic growth and job creation. (Kumar et al., 2024)Despite standard limits, this idea includes both innovative improvements to current operations and completely original inventions that greatly increase output or product offerings. Henry Ford, for example, is frequently credited with creating assembly line production, a game-changing invention that led to large efficiency gains and

became the basis for today's manufacturing (Glaeser & Lang, 2023). However, studies highlight that the impact of innovation is dependent to both novelty and the successful integration of new concepts into preexisting environments (Baldwin et al., 2024). The increasing use of digital platforms has brought attention to the significance of collaborative ecosystems, where value creation is improved by the combined efforts by multiple stakeholders rather than by their individual efforts (Vargo et al., 2024). While innovation promotes growth, this cooperative approach highlights that its success usually depends on a supportive atmosphere that encourages collaboration and flexibility.

2.2.2. Importance of innovation in firms

For businesses to remain competitive, adapt to changes in the market, and achieve sustainable growth, innovation is essential. Innovation helps a business improve its organisational structures and knowledge management skills, which allows it to create new goods and improve service quality which are two essentials for maintaining a competitive edge in marketplaces (Cakir et al., 2024; Hassan, 2016; Hassan, 2023; Hassan, 2019; Haddad and Hassan, 2025). Furthermore, innovation helps companies in implementing digital solutions that can improve overall performance by improving efficiency and reducing expenses (Ferreira et al., 2024). In industries such as high technology, open innovation has emerged as an essential approach that allows businesses to work with outside partners to exchange knowledge, lower R&D expenses, and faster the launch of new goods. In order to react effectively to technology advancements, this partnership enhances agility and encourages innovation (Song & Kim, 2024). However, there are some studies think that a firm's internal capacity for effectively implementing new knowledge is just as important to innovation success as external resources or teamwork. Because the value of external knowledge is only really realised when it aligns with a firm's internal strategy, even open innovation could face limitations in the absence of strong internal structures and a culture that encourages knowledge-sharing (Erhan et al., 2024).

2.3.3. Challenges of innovations in firms

Innovation is a key factor in business expansion, but many companies face significant challenges along the way. High-tech businesses frequently deal with excessive expenses and a lack of internal resources, which may lead them to look for outside partnerships. For female entrepreneurs, who often find it difficult to get the networks and capital required to promote

innovation, this difficulty is much greater (Song & Kim, 2024). In the same way, highlight how crucial distributed government is to innovation management. Several stakeholders collaborate on decision-making in this model, resulting in a flexible structure that promotes expansion. However, these collaborative ecosystems are frequently inaccessible to female entrepreneurs, which can hinder their capacity for effective innovation (Vargo et al., 2024). In the microfinance industry, financial limitations provide an important barrier since organisations find it difficult to implement innovations based on data because they have limited access to modern instruments. For women-led enterprises, who have extra challenges in getting the financial and technological resources required for innovation, this problem is especially severe (Hani et al., 2024). operational inefficiencies also contribute to the uneven outcomes of gamification, a technique designed to encourage innovation and participation. Women entrepreneurs are more heavily impacted by these inefficiencies, which make it more difficult to maintain long-term innovative efforts (Abril et al., 2024). The problem is made worse by financial risks as there is higher research and development spending increases the cost of equity, which already places a greater burden on female entrepreneurs, facing leading biases and restrictive financial terms.(Zhang et al., 2024).

2.3. Limitation of women's entrepreneur's innovation

Women entrepreneurs' capacity to innovate is hindered by a number of obstacles. They often face trouble obtaining funds since it can be more difficult to obtain loans or investments due to gender bias. They also face challenges caused by a lack of networks and mentors, which reduces their opportunities to exchange ideas and seek guidance. Family obligations and cultural standards put more pressure on them, making it difficult to concentrate on their companies. Many are also pushed out of high growth sectors due to biases in the business world and lack of expertise in specific areas. Women find it more difficult to realise new ideas because of these obstacles.

2.3.1 Internal factors

In Egypt, internal factors seriously limit the potential of female entrepreneurs to innovate. Social biases frequently cause women to distrust their own skills, which prevents them from pursuing ambitious ideas, therefore self-confidence is crucial (Stanković et al.,2023).The problem is made worse by familial responsibilities, and cultural norms prevent women from

dedicating much time or effort to their businesses, which limits their innovation (Hassan & Almubarak, 2016; Naguib, 2022). Additionally, many people run away from taking chances, preferring stability over the unpredictability required for innovation, which restricts competitiveness and growth (Meyer, 2022). Also emotional intelligence is beneficial for relationships and teamwork, but it frequently shifts attention from overcoming systemic obstacles like money and support (Farroñán et al.,2024). For people to realise their potential for creativity, these problems must be addressed through cultural changes and support programs.

2.3.1.1 Self confidences

Self-confidence improves leadership and decision-making abilities, which are critical for starting and managing creative actions (Bruhin et al., 2024). Which makes confidence essential for empowering female entrepreneurs since it allows them to take chances and be innovative. Strongly confident women are more likely to go against gender norms and achieve success in entrepreneurship because they have faith in their capacity to overcome obstacles (Stanković et al.,2023) By empowering women to face innovative problems and start new businesses, particularly when faced with challenges. Self-confidence allows women to turn creative ideas into profitable projects (Cabrera & Mauricio,2017) In Egypt, women entrepreneurs have shown this by using their confidence to enter competitive industries, where they challenge gender norms by implementing innovative ideas and run profitable firms (Stanković et al.,2023). However, when women's self-confidence is restricted by family-related and cultural obstacles, criticism occurs Entrepreneurial skills is frequently hindered by cultural expectations, especially in traditional environments like Egypt where family obligations may prevent them from exploring creative business paths. To sum up, many women can still find it difficult to get past the outside obstacles that keep them from reaching their full creative potential ,even when women are confident enough to create, these cultural limitations still restrict their business potential reducing their potential for innovation and growth(Farroñán et al.,2024).It is more difficult for individuals to overcome obstacles when they lack mentors, supporting networks, and resources that can improve their self-confidence (Bruhin et al., 2024).

2.3.1.2. Family responsibility

In the social environment of emerging countries, women's involvement in business activities makes it difficult to balance work and family obligations. (Khan et al., 2021). One important factor that could affect a woman's involvement is her family. Women may be unable or able to grow their businesses based on family responsibility, as women have responsibilities to care for their families and must handle all issues equally. (Khalid et al., 2020). The stress of balancing job and family obligations affects their capacity for strategic planning and long-term goal concentration (Dewitt et al., 2023). Similar problems occur in nations like Bangladesh and Morocco, where women are limited in their ability to innovate due to social pressures to put their families before their careers (Naguib, 2022). Although they are uncommon and don't address the underlying issue, supportive family structures can occasionally be helpful in locations like Alabnia (Ahmetaj et al., 2023). So, social norms frequently assign women sole responsibility for taking care of the home and children, leaving them with little time or energy for economic activities, which hinders creativity and innovation (Hassan & Almubarak, 2016). These obstacles will continue to prevent female entrepreneurs from realising their full potential without changes such as flexible laws, reasonably priced childcare, and a change in cultural perceptions.

2.3.1.3 Risk taking

One important aspect of entrepreneurial innovation is risk-taking, which encourages people to face uncertainty and explore new possibilities. Risk-taking entrepreneurs tend to be better able to adjust, try new things, and come up with creative solutions that differentiate their companies from competitors (Saeedikiya et al., 2024). Also women typically stay away of high-risk efforts, which leads to lower investments and fewer opportunities for innovation, especially if faced with maternity and family obligations (Core, 2024). women who had a positive attitude towards taking risks were more likely to innovate and launch their own companies. This highlights the importance of creating conditions that support women in taking risks (Yoopetch, 2021). However, women's capacity to innovate is frequently limited by institutional and societal limitations, forcing them to concentrate on less disruptive, safer projects (Rivera et al., 2024). To sum up, risk taking influence women entrepreneurs' capability for innovation because of cultural expectations and a fear of failing, women are frequently less willing than

males to take chances. This hesitancy is linked to cultural norms and a lack of self-assurance, which seriously limits their capacity for creativity and entrepreneurship (Zeffane, 2015)

2.3.1.4. Emotional intelligence

Since emotional intelligence (EI) allows people to effectively control their emotions and handle challenging environments, it is an essential factor in encouraging innovation. Emotionally intelligent people are better able to deal with failures, adapt to changes, and handle problems creatively (Winton & Sabol, 2024). Which makes emotional intelligence (EI) a significant factor in determining how innovative women entrepreneurs may be. In order to encourage innovation in their organisations, women with high EI are better at managing teams, handling stress, and making decisions (Kovid et al., 2024). Emotional intelligence (EI) increases self-efficacy and confidence, empowering women to take on new tasks and carry out innovative ideas, especially in unpredictable situations (Mortan et al., 2014). However, It also shows how women use emotional intelligence (EI) to create strong networks and connections, which are both critical for promoting creativity. that women with high emotional intelligence (EI) are abler to recover back from failures, adapt, and find new methods to succeed (Mishra & Singh, 2022). So to sum up despite their emotional intelligence, women entrepreneurs may find it difficult to show their abilities in businesses with a high percentage of men due to cultural biases, such as social norms often put extra stress on women, need to balance work and family obligations, which may reduce the emotional energy required for company innovation. So all this can limit their potential for innovation (Chaidi et al., 2022).

2.3.2. External factors

The traditional belief that only men should manage a business, a lack of funding, and rejection from sexist informal networks are some of the external challenges faced by Egyptian women entrepreneurs. Usually, these limits result from cultural customs, beliefs, and values (Hassan, 2018).

Furthermore, a lot of uncertainty exists in both the political and economic areas, which makes it very difficult for female investors to make judgements (Khan, et al., 2021). Besides getting material resources like finance and real estate, women have faced continuous barriers to education, market expertise, and modern technologies. So the types of businesses that women participate in are negatively impacted by all of these factors (Sajuyigbe & Fadeyibi, 2017).

2.3.2.1. Access to financial

For entrepreneurs, access to financing is an important driver of innovation since it gives them the opportunity to explore and successfully develop new ideas. Many entrepreneurs find it difficult to bring their ideas to life without sufficient funding, especially in developing nations (Fombang & Adjasi, 2018). One of the biggest obstacles limiting Egyptian women entrepreneurs' creativity is access to funding. In order to invest in new ideas and expand the businesses they own, women are usually subjected to stricter loan requirements, higher interest rates, and discrimination based on gender in financing (Garg et al., 2023). Most of banks don't rely on women to provide business loans, and when they do, security is usually required. Having access to loans could help encourage more women to launch their own business (Khalid, et.al.,2020). Many choose to self-finance because government financing is hard to get, which makes it harder to grow and innovate (KHALEQUE, 2018). This problem gets worse by women's inability to effectively understand funding choices due to a lack of financial knowledge (Dsouza & Panakaje,2023). However, measures intended for removing these obstacles appear promising. In some developing countries, for example, programs like microcredit programs and reserved rights for women have improved access to capital and encouraged creativity among female entrepreneurs (Emon & Nipa, 2024).Moreover, these efforts fail to address institutional problems that maintain these inequalities, such as gender bias in financial institutions (Garg et al., 2023)so to sum up, their inability to grow their firms or invest in creative solutions is a result of this access inequality so financial limitations have a direct effect on women entrepreneurs' firm success (Aliyu et al., 2019)

2.3.2.2. Socio cultural

The term "socio-cultural" refers to the different external cultural elements that are linked to the influence of an employee's personality on a company and the uncertainty of the economy (Khan, et al.,2021). Due to sociocultural barriers that support traditional gender roles and societal expectations. Women's time, flexibility, and networking opportunities are restricted because they are often seen primarily as caretakers. Social norms prevent women from choosing careers in fields where men dominate, which restricts their ability to innovate (Anggadwita et al., 2017). Furthermore, women often come under pressure from cultural norms to manage domestic duties with entrepreneurship, which adds to their stress levels and hinders from their focus on expanding their businesses (Cullen, 2019).to sum up these social influences often lead women to choose small, unregistered firms that fit to cultural standards over high-

growth or creative businesses (Sobhan & Hassan, 2024) And because of these limitations, women-driven businesses tend to be smaller and less technologically advanced than those managed by males (Badghish et al., 2023).

2.3.2.3. Gender discrimination

When people suffer from unfair or uneven treatment because of their gender, it is known as gender discrimination and results in differences in opportunities and achievements. This can include inequalities in pay, job opportunities, or educational opportunities (Lundberg, 2022). Moreover, gender discrimination is a major barrier that limits the innovative potential of female entrepreneurs. Due to established stereotypes in the world of entrepreneurship, women tend to stick to less creative industries like retail and education, which present fewer chances for high-impact innovation (Rivera et al., 2024). Women have obstacles when it comes to getting digital tools and technology, which are essential for implementing new practices (Suseno & Abbott, 2021). Because women are frequently turned down by investors or forced to more strict standards, discrimination also impacts funding opportunities, causing many to turn to self-financing or give up on their plans completely (Veckalne & Tambovceva, 2023). However, despite efforts to reduce the gender gap through campaigning and policy, systemic biases that still hinder women's progress and innovation are frequently ignored (Mari et al., 2024).

2.3.2.4. Networking ability

The capacity to build and use connections to gain support and promote teamwork is known as networking ability. It is essential to get funding and forming partnerships which allow concepts to be transformed into practical technologies that support the goals of the company (Mu et al., 2017). Networking is essential for encouraging creativity among female entrepreneurs, but it is still quite difficult. Due to social barriers and limited access to professional circles, many women find it difficult to establish strong networks, which limits their access to resources, opinions, and collaborative opportunities (Aliyu et al., 2019). Relying on informal networks usually restricts women-led firms' being exposed to a variety of opportunities and viewpoints, even though good networking can significantly help them by expanding access to market knowledge and creative ideas (Thousani & Edy, 2023). Although, while networking promotes innovation in markets and products, focusing too much on connected networks can lead to inefficiency and decrease chances of obtaining new opportunities (Sadraei, 2024). Which

makes women in male-dominated fields commonly face obstacles when trying to access high-value networks, which reduces the opportunity for innovation.(Rivera et al., 2024)

2.4 Research gap

Although a lot of research has been done on the challenges faced by female entrepreneurs around the world, little is known about how these difficulties especially affect Egyptian women entrepreneurs' ability to innovate. The majority of researches from areas like South Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, and the larger MENA region focusses common barriers such a lack of networking possibilities, constrictive cultural norms, and trouble obtaining financing (GEM, 2021). These studies, however, tend to ignore the unusual interaction of institutional, cultural, and economic elements that influence Egypt's entrepreneurial culture. Mainly, more study is required to understand how these external obstacles interact with internal elements including risk-taking behaviours, emotional intelligence, and self-confidence. According to study, for example, women's creativity and innovation can be reduced by external obstacles such as monetary limitations and gender discrimination, which may increase internal conflicts (Bastian & Zali, 2016). Although the literature is expanding, not many studies have looked at the Egyptian setting in its whole. This is because women entrepreneurs face a unique mix of obstacles due to governmental gaps, family responsibilities, and societal expectations (Borham et al., 2024; Elkafrawi & Refai, 2022). Furthermore, previous research often focuses on high-level obstacles without providing specific details into how Egyptian women overcome these obstacles and how they affect creativity. Though there isn't much actual evidence to support these efforts in Egypt, studies indicate that targeted efforts like mentorship programs, fair funding regulations, and cultural changes may reduce these obstacles (Khalid et al., 2020; Naguib, 2024). This difference highlights how crucial it is to learn how internal and external forces interact to limit creativity and the success of entrepreneurs. By studying specific challenges experienced by Egyptian women entrepreneurs, this study seeks to close these gaps. This study aims to give an in depth understanding of the obstacles to women's innovation in Egypt by focusing on the interaction between internal elements like emotional intelligence and self-confidence and external ones like cultural standards. By doing this, it will add on gender equality, innovation, and entrepreneurship while providing stakeholders and policymakers with useful information to build more encouraging environments.

Research Questions

What are the main barriers to innovation among Egyptian women entrepreneurs, and how do these internal and external factors connect to affect their ability for innovation?

3. Methodology

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the study's methodology is described. In regard to this, the areas of the study are discussed together with the considerations which led to the selection of the specific area. This chapter provides an explanation of the population, sample, and sampling strategies as well as the data collection methodologies used. The methods used to collect and analyse the data, as well as the methods used for confirming the instruments, are also described.

3.2 Research Design

In the examination of the research plan structure, the research design describes the procedure for gathering information. While the search approach is the input activity, the research strategy acts as a barrier between the research topic and its success. (Khalid et al., 2020). An exploratory qualitative design is used in this study to explore the barriers to innovation faced by Egyptian women entrepreneurs. This method is perfect for learning more about the lived experiences and viewpoints of women because these obstacles are complicated and poorly understood. Exploratory qualitative research, in contrast to quantitative approaches, helps us to identify topics, patterns, and details that could otherwise go missed (Peterson, 2019; Papasavva et al., 2021). Semi-structured interviews are performed to gather data. This approach combines an established set of questions with the freedom to change them in response to participants' answers. For this kind of research, semi-structured interviews are very helpful since they let participants tell deeply, intimate experiences while maintaining consistency throughout the entire interview. Understanding the special challenges faced by female entrepreneurs requires achieving a balance between structure and openness (Peterson, 2019).

3.3 Sampling design

Egyptian women entrepreneurs are the target population. Since the limitations under study have a direct impact on these women, their opinions are essential for understanding the difficulties preventing innovation.

Non-probability sampling techniques, including judgmental, snowball, and convenience sampling, are used in the study. Snowball sampling makes sure that hard-to-reach people are reached through referrals, while convenience sampling assists in finding participants who are willing and able to participate. Judgmental sampling ensures that participants are relevant to the study, which focusses on women who are actively involved in business.

10 to 12 female entrepreneurs from a range of background and industries will make up the sample. This size makes it possible for deep qualitative research while ensuring sufficient data to determine key issues. Including people from diverse industries and demographics provides a wide range of viewpoints, improving the results.

3.4 Instrument Development

The interview questions were designed to explore the challenges that limit innovation among female entrepreneurs in Egypt. To make sure all areas were covered, the questions were divided into four main sections: general background, internal factors, external factors, and creativity and innovation. This helped guide the conversation and allowed each participant to share their experience in detail.

The first section focused on general background. It aimed to understand each woman's story, why she started her business, what motivated her, and what the journey has been like so far. Questions like "Can you introduce yourself by sharing your name, age, industry, and how you started your business?" helped give context and insight into each participant's entrepreneurial path.

The second part focused on internal factors. These included things like self-confidence, emotional intelligence, family responsibilities, and willingness to take risks. For example, questions such as "How does self-confidence influence your ability to make decisions and introduce new ideas?" or "Have family responsibilities ever made it harder for you to focus on innovation?" were asked. The goal was to understand how their mindset and personal situations affected their ability to innovate.

The third section covered external factors. This included financial limitations, supplier challenges, gender discrimination, cultural expectations, and access to networks or mentors. Questions like "Have you ever faced discrimination in business because you're a woman?" and

“What challenges have you faced while trying to get funding?” helped reveal the external obstacles many women deal with in their business environment.

The final section explored how the participants view innovation. It asked about the creative ideas they tried to implement, what worked, and what didn't. For example, questions like “Can you give an example of an innovation you successfully implemented?” and “What factors limit your ability to innovate?” were included. This part helped show how they define creativity and what blocks them from turning their ideas into action.

Overall, organizing the interview this way helped keep things focused but flexible. Each woman was able to speak freely while still covering all the areas that matter for the research.

3.5 Procedure

To better understand the challenges that female entrepreneurs in Egypt face when trying to innovate, I followed a qualitative research approach. This type of study was chosen because it allows people to express their real experiences and stories, which was important for a topic like this.

First, I reached out to potential participants through social media, professional circles, and entrepreneurship events. Once someone agreed to join, I explained the purpose of the study and made sure to get their written consent before starting the interview.

The interviews were semi-structured, meaning I had a set of questions but also allowed the conversation to flow naturally. Depending on what worked best for each participant, interviews were done either call or face-to-face. Each one lasted around 15 to 20 minutes and was recorded with permission to ensure I didn't miss anything important during analysis.

The interview usually started with general questions to make the participant feel comfortable. Then, we moved on to deeper questions related to the internal and external barriers they face. After all interviews were completed, I listened back to the recordings, took notes, and analyzed the answers.

I looked for common themes and patterns across all interviews. Some challenges came up more than once, like financial struggles, gender bias from suppliers, fear of failure, and the pressure of cultural norms. On the other hand, things like emotional intelligence, support from family,

and strong networking also stood out as helpful factors in overcoming obstacles and finding new ideas.

By organizing and comparing these insights, I was able to understand not just what barriers exist, but how these women think, react, and find ways to innovate in difficult situations. This made the results more meaningful and real.

Table 1 identifying all interview participants

Interview	Industry	Years running the business	Employment status
1	Fashion	3 year	Founder & Employee
2	Fashion	1 year	Founder & Student
3	Fashion	3 years	Founder & Employee
4	Home fragrances	1 year	Founder & Employee
5	Handicrafts	5 years	Founder & Employee
6	Handicrafts & Fashion	3 years	Founder & Student
7	Fashion (Kids/Teens)	1 years	Founder & Student
8	Fashion	3 years	Founder & Employee
9	Stationery	2 year	Founder & Employed
10	Marketing services	1 years	Self Employed
11	Stationery	2 years	Founder & Employee

Interview Analysis

Theme	Interviewee Name	Quotes
Self-Confidence and Risk-Taking	Sana El Basha	“Confidence is everything. If you don’t believe in yourself, you won’t take risks... I wasn’t sure how it would go, but I believed in the idea and trusted myself.”
	Menna Eid	“Without self-confidence, we wouldn’t have had the courage to push forward and launch our unique ideas.”
	Rawda Magdy	“Self-confidence helped me stand by my vision for modest fashion and interact assertively in uncomfortable professional settings like factories.”
	Reem Hussein	“If you’re not confident, people can easily make you doubt your vision.”
	Safy Mohamed	“In the beginning, I feared how people would react to my ideas, but as I saw positive feedback, my confidence grew.”
	Areej Tarek	“If I feel unsure about my product, it shows... But once I trusted myself, things started to improve.”
	Hana Ali	“I used to doubt myself, but after sharing my ideas and getting positive feedback, I gained more confidence.”
	Sarah Gamal	“Self-confidence is everything. Whether it’s pitching your idea or sticking to your design vision you need confidence to not be swayed.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“If you’re not confident in yourself or your product, you can’t market it.” & “I gained more self-confidence after becoming partners with Clara. That helped us expand our business.”
	Suhaila	“If a client senses you’re not confident, they won’t believe in what you’re offering. That confidence makes all the difference.”

Fear of Failure	Sana El Basha	“My biggest fear was launching something that no one would buy.”
	Menna Eid	“There were fears especially about how people would receive something different like metalwork.”
	Rawda Magdy	“She feared that there would be low demand for her modest clothing.”
	Reem Hussein	“I struggled when I wanted to introduce a linen spray... getting people to accept something different.”
	Safy Mohamed	“I worried about the time and effort. Sometimes, my ideas would change along the way.”
	Areej Tarek	“I was scared people wouldn’t buy the car caddy or something would go wrong with the product.”
	Hana Ali	“I was afraid people wouldn’t like what I was offering... my main concern was launching something no one wanted.”
	Sarah Gamal	“I had a winter collection in mind, but I didn’t go through with it because I was afraid it wouldn’t work.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“We wanted to launch a summer kit but got scared it might not work, so we didn’t do it.”
	Suhaila	“I was scared of failing, but eventually I just decided to try.”
Family Responsibilities and Time Limitations	Sana El Basha	“I had to skip a lot of family gatherings because I needed to catch up on orders.”
	Menna Eid	“I’m still a student, so I don’t have major family responsibilities yet.”

	Rawda Magdy	“Balancing my job, home life, and the business is really hard.”
	Reem Hussein	“Ramadan was a challenge family gatherings distracted me from work.”
	Safy Mohamed	“At first, I gave all my time to the business and paid less attention to my children.”
	Areej Tarek	“Sometimes I didn’t have the time or energy to focus, so I would just write my ideas for later.”
	Hana Ali	“My family expects me to be more present at home, even when I have deadlines.”
	Sarah Gamal	“I always feel like I have to prove to my family that I’ll succeed.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“Our parents didn’t understand the business at first, so we worked harder to prove it’s serious.”
	Suhaila	“In the beginning, I barely saw my family. I had no weekends.”
Financial Limitations	Sana El Basha	"Yes, many times. In the beginning, I didn’t have much knowledge or funds. But having the support of my family made all the difference."
	Menna Eid	"Yes, we faced financial challenges because we’re both just 21. But we worked

		through it by setting a clear budget and sticking to it."
	Rawda Magdy	"Yes. Modest clothing needs more fabric, which increases costs. I had to search a lot to find affordable suppliers."
	Reem Hussein	"Yes, financial challenges are real. Sometimes you want to do something new but don't have the money. I had to start small and be smart about where I spend."
	Safy Mohamed	"Thankfully, I haven't faced serious financial limitations that stopped me from launching new ideas."
	Areej Tarek	"Definitely. I never liked relying on my mom for money, so I worked, saved up, and only started when I had enough."
	Hana Ali	"Yes, launching a business requires a lot of capital. I managed by turning to my family for financial support."
	Sarah Gamal	"Definitely. I was scared to spend too much on production or models, so I asked girls I know who wanted to model. That kept costs low."
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	"Honestly, no. We haven't faced serious financial issues when launching new products."
	Suhaila	"Yes, of course. Sometimes clients want results with a tight budget. I offered solutions step-by-step within what they could afford."

Gender Discrimination and Social Pressure	Sana El Basha	“Yes, especially from suppliers. They tend to underestimate women or act like we don’t know what we’re doing. From customers, it’s not that noticeable because they usually don’t know who the owner is.”
	Menna Eid	“Yes. Women face extra barriers, especially with suppliers. When they see us as young women, they raise prices or don’t take us seriously.”
	Rawda Magdy	“Yes. In factories, men often treated her as if she didn’t understand business, simply because she was a woman.”
	Reem Hussein	“I didn’t face discrimination from investors, but with suppliers, yes. Sometimes I felt harassed or not taken seriously just because I’m a woman.”
	Safy Mohamed	“Yes. There were instances where clients didn’t take me seriously but treated my male partner differently.”
	Areej Tarek	“Yes, I’ve had suppliers refuse to sell me materials or claim they didn’t have something — only for me to later find it elsewhere.”
	Hana Ali	“Yes, especially from suppliers. Some of them treat women differently they doubt us or act like we’re not serious.”
	Sarah Gamal	“Yes, especially with suppliers and factories. They don’t take you seriously at first.”

	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“Actually, the opposite. People have been very supportive. They give us advice and try to help. We didn’t face any discrimination.”
	Suhaila	“I wouldn’t call it direct discrimination, but meetings happen at night or in certain male-dominated settings it’s not always comfortable or practical for women to attend.”
Lack of Networks and Mentorship	Sana El Basha	“Yes, I did face challenges. It’s hard to find real mentors or networks that support women-led businesses.”
	Menna Eid	“Without networking, many of our ideas would’ve stayed ideas we wouldn’t have had the tools to make them real.”
	Rawda Magdy	“Networking has been very important. It helped me find better factories with reasonable prices.”
	Reem Hussein	“I connected with influencers and people with large followings, which helped me a lot.”
	Safy Mohamed	“Good relationships have helped me promote my work. Friends often recommend me.”
	Areej Tarek	“At first, I didn’t know where to go or who to connect with, but by visiting different places, I built a network.”
	Hana Ali	“It was hard to access networks and mentors, but I started reaching out online

		and things became easier.”
	Sarah Gamal	“Through friends and connections, I found good photographers, got supplier contacts, and met people who helped me.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“Networking is very important. Most of our opportunities came from people we already knew.”
	Suhaila	“Most of my early clients came through people I knew or had worked with. 80% of my business came from word of mouth.”
Innovation Despite the Challenges	Sana El Basha	“I introduced a product line people didn’t understand at first, but after trying it, it became a best seller.”
	Menna Eid	“Our handcrafted metal pieces were new and risky, but now they’re what makes us unique.”
	Rawda Magdy	“I launched modest pieces that reflect our culture and style. They became part of the brand’s identity.”
	Reem Hussein	“I introduced reed diffusers, even though people were used to candles. That’s what made my brand stand out.”
	Safy Mohamed	“I turned leftover fabric into something beautiful using embroidery. It was a challenge to see value in waste.”

	Areej Tarek	“I changed how people saw crochet. I made it unisex and more relatable.”
	Hana Ali	“I made coloring kits on toothbrush packaging for kids. It became both a fun activity and part of our marketing.”
	Sarah Gamal	“My oversized modest t-shirts were new in style and fit. They became our best sellers.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“The memory book was something new people loved writing, drawing, and saving photos all in one product.”
	Suhaila	“I always research my client’s industry first. That’s how I offer ideas they haven’t seen before.”
Emotional Intelligence and Coping with Stress	Sana El Basha	“Emotional intelligence helps me manage stress and separate personal emotions from work. It keeps me focused under pressure.”
	Menna Eid	“When things get hard, we step back, take a break, and reset. Emotional awareness helps us deal with stress and stay motivated.”
	Rawda Magdy	“I avoid stress by not overloading myself. Emotional intelligence helps me stay calm and keep things under control.”
	Reem Hussein	“I go to therapy and talk to my family. Emotional intelligence helps me

		understand how I feel and how I treat people.”
	Safy Mohamed	“I make sure to stay calm with clients, even when I’m stressed. Emotional control is important for keeping a good image.”
	Areej Tarek	“When I feel pressure, I try to finish the task and then reflect. That helps me understand the stress and learn from it.”
	Hana Ali	“I lean on my family and friends for support. I’ve learned not to let hard days take control of me.”
	Sarah Gamal	“I’ve learned to stay calm and solve problems. Letting my emotions take over would’ve slowed me down.”
	Clara Ayman & Radwa Mohamed	“When we’re stressed, we pause and reset. Being emotionally aware helps us keep a clear mind as a team.”
	Suhaila	“When I’m overwhelmed, I take space to protect my mindset. If I break down emotionally, my team will feel it too.”

4. Results and Findings

This section presents the main findings from the ten interviews conducted with Egyptian women entrepreneurs working in different industries . Through thematic analysis, I was able to identify common patterns and themes that reflect the main challenges these women face when trying to innovate. These challenges were both internal like self-confidence and fear of failure and external like lack of finance, social pressure, and limited networks. Despite the obstacles, many women still managed to be creative and find ways to move forward.

Self-Confidence and Risk-Taking

Almost every woman I spoke to mentioned how important confidence was when starting something new. Confidence, they said, was what gave them the push to take a risk, to try an idea that others doubted, or to speak up when it felt uncomfortable.

Sana (Interviewee 1) said it straight up: “Confidence is everything. If you don’t believe in yourself, you won’t take risks.” She told me how she launched a product even though she wasn’t sure how people would react but believing in herself gave her the courage to go for it.

Menna (Interviewee 2), who co-founded a fashion brand, also said, “Without self-confidence, we wouldn’t have had the courage to push forward and launch our unique ideas.” For Rawda (Interviewee 3), confidence helped her navigate awkward interactions in male-dominated spaces like factories: “Self-confidence helped me stand by my vision for modest fashion and interact assertively.”

Some women said confidence didn’t come naturally it grew over time. Safy (Interviewee 5) told me, “At first, I feared how people would react, but once I saw some positive feedback, my confidence grew.” And Areej (Interviewee 6) added, “If I feel unsure about my product, it shows. But once I trusted myself, things started to improve.”

Fear of Failure

Fear of failure was something that came up again and again. Many women admitted they hesitated to launch something new because they were scared of rejection, of financial loss, or of simply not being good enough.

Sana (Interviewee 1) told me honestly, “My biggest fear was launching something that no one would buy.” Menna (Interviewee 2) also shared her doubts: “There were fears especially about how people would receive something different like metalwork.”

Reem (Interviewee 4) spoke about trying to introduce a linen spray in a market that wasn’t familiar with such products. She said, “It was hard to convince people to try something small and different from what they were used to.”

What really stood out, though, was that most of these women didn't let fear stop them. They found ways to move forward by starting small, testing their ideas, and learning to trust themselves over time.

Family Responsibilities and Time Limitations

Family responsibilities were another big theme, but the impact varied depending on age and life stage. Some of the younger participants like Menna and Rawda said they didn't have major family obligations yet, so they had more time to focus on their businesses.

But for others, especially those with kids, it was a different story. Safy (Interviewee 5) shared, "I was responsible for raising my four children and that took a lot of my time and energy." Reem (Interviewee 4) also mentioned that "family gatherings and responsibilities distracted me from my business, especially during Ramadan."

Even when families were supportive, the emotional and physical pressure of balancing both roles definitely affected how much time they could dedicate to new ideas or business growth.

Financial Limitations

Money was by far one of the most mentioned barriers. Almost every woman I spoke to had creative ideas they couldn't fully bring to life because of financial limitations. Whether it was packaging, marketing, or developing a new product funding was often the missing piece.

Sana (Interviewee 1) said, "In the beginning, I didn't have much knowledge or funds. But having the support of my family made all the difference." Menna (Interviewee 2) added, "We worked through financial challenges by setting a clear budget and sticking to it."

For many, not having access to proper funding made them more cautious. It slowed down their ability to experiment or scale their ideas quickly.

Gender Discrimination and Social Pressure

Unfortunately, gender bias was something that many women experienced firsthand. Most said it showed up clearly when dealing with suppliers or service providers.

Sana (Interviewee 1) told me, “Suppliers tend to underestimate women or act like we don’t know what we’re doing.” Menna (Interviewee 2) echoed this: “They treat us differently because we’re women higher prices, slower responses, or not believing in our vision.”

Even though these experiences were frustrating, many participants didn’t let them stop their progress. They learned to stand up for themselves, ask for help, or find better people to work with.

Lack of Networks and Mentorship

Many women said they struggled in the beginning because they didn’t know where to go for advice or support. Some wished there were programs or mentors specifically for women starting out.

Sana (Interviewee 1) explained: “It’s hard to find real mentors or networks that support women-led businesses.” Menna (Interviewee 2) added, “Without networking, many of our ideas would’ve stayed ideas. We wouldn’t have had the tools to make them real.”

While some eventually found support online or through communities, it was clear that this lack of access made the journey harder and slower.

Innovation Despite the Challenges

One of the most inspiring parts of this research was seeing how these women still found ways to innovate, even with limited resources.

Sana (Interviewee 1) shared how she launched a completely new product that people didn’t understand at first. But once they tried it, it became one of her best sellers. “It gave us a new identity and expanded our customer base,” she said.

Reem (Interviewee 4) used fun packaging designs to attract kids and parents. Others talked about adding small personal touches to customer service or using trending content on social media to increase engagement.

These stories proved that innovation doesn’t always require a big budget it just takes creativity and a deep understanding of what your customers need.

Emotional Intelligence and Coping with Stress

Finally, emotional intelligence came up as an important skill for dealing with all the pressure that comes with running a business.

Interviewee 7 shared: “Emotional intelligence allows me to manage my emotions, separate personal life from work, and make better decisions under pressure.” And Interviewee 8 said, “Stress affected my ability to introduce new ideas at first, but I later learned how to deal with pressure more calmly.”

Many of the women talked about journaling, taking breaks, or talking to family and friends when things got overwhelming. This emotional strength helped them stay grounded and make thoughtful decisions even in tough situations.

4.1 Discussion

This research aimed to explore the internal and external factors that limit innovation among Egyptian women entrepreneurs. After reviewing the literature, several key barriers were identified such as lack of confidence, family pressure, financial limitations, social expectations, and limited access to support. These barriers were confirmed and further explained through the analysis of 11 interviews with women entrepreneurs in Egypt and other studies on barriers to start business (Bruhin et al., 2024; Hassan, 2018).

One of the main findings was the importance of self-confidence. Most participants said that when they trusted themselves, they were more likely to try new ideas or take risks (Cabrera & Mauricio, 2017). However, many women shared that their confidence was not always strong in the beginning, especially when they felt judged or unsupported by others (Stanković et al., 2023). Over time, their confidence grew through experience and positive customer feedback, which encouraged them to take bolder steps (Bruhin et al., 2024).

Closely linked to self-confidence was the willingness to take risks. Many of the women were cautious when trying something new and expressed fear of failure, especially because of social criticism or market uncertainty (Zeffane, 2015). In a traditional society like Egypt, women are often taught to play it safe, which makes them more hesitant to launch unfamiliar or bold ideas (Saeedikiya et al., 2024). Still, some women managed to take small steps and slowly test new concepts, which helped them overcome this fear (Bruhin et al., 2024).

Family responsibilities were also a major theme. Some women, especially those with children, found it hard to balance between their business and personal life (Khan et al., 2021). While some families were supportive and helped financially or emotionally, the pressure to succeed without disappointing loved ones added stress (Hassan & Almubarak, 2016). This dual pressure support and expectation created emotional tension that sometimes slowed down innovation (Dewitt et al., 2023).

Another key factor was emotional intelligence, which helped women deal with stress and manage difficult situations (Winton & Sabol, 2024). Participants said that staying calm under pressure, being aware of their emotions, and knowing how to manage relationships were important for staying focused and moving their businesses forward (Mortan et al., 2014). While emotional intelligence didn't directly lead to innovation, it created the mental space for it to happen (Chaidi et al., 2022).

On the external side, financial limitations were among the biggest barriers. Most women said they funded their businesses using their own savings or help from family (Nasir et al., 2019). Many avoided banks because of strict loan conditions, lack of collateral, or lack of trust (Khalid et al., 2020). Even though some financial programs exist, women said they didn't know how to access them or found the process too complicated (Dsouza & Panakaje, 2023). This lack of funding slowed down innovation or forced women to delay or reduce their ideas (Nasir et al., 2019).

Cultural and social expectations also played a big role. Several participants said they felt judged for being ambitious, working long hours, or stepping into male-dominated spaces (Elkafrawi & Refai, 2022). Some women shared that they had to always appear "perfect" to be taken seriously (Anggadwita et al., 2017). These expectations affected how freely they could make decisions or experiment with new ideas (Rivera et al., 2024).

In addition, many women faced gender discrimination. Some were ignored, overcharged, or treated unfairly by male suppliers and business partners (Rivera et al., 2024). They said they had to prove themselves more than men to be respected or taken seriously (Khalid et al., 2020). This discrimination made their journey harder, even though they worked just as hard to grow and innovate (Stanković et al., 2023).

Finally, networking was seen as both a challenge and an opportunity. Women who had mentors, social media exposure, or participated in bazaars found it easier to get resources and support

(Aliyu et al., 2019). But others said they didn't know where to find help or were excluded from male-dominated networks (Sadraei, 2024). Even though some women managed to build informal networks, it often took more time and effort (Rivera et al., 2024).

To sum up, this research showed that women entrepreneurs in Egypt face a mix of internal and external challenges that limit their ability to innovate. Internal factors like confidence, emotional pressure, and family obligations are deeply linked with external ones like money, culture, and access to networks (Nasir et al., 2019). While many of the women showed strong creativity and motivation, their environment often made it harder for them to grow freely or take new steps (Khalid et al., 2020). These results confirm much of the existing research but also give deeper insight into the Egyptian context.

4.2 Limitation

No study is perfect, and this one has its own limitations too. The first limitation is the small sample size. This research was based on 11 in-depth interviews with women entrepreneurs, and while their stories were meaningful and insightful, they cannot represent the experiences of all female entrepreneurs across Egypt. The aim was to understand lived experiences in depth, not to make generalizations about the entire population. Another limitation is related to geographical diversity. Most participants were based in Cairo and nearby urban areas. As a result, the study may not fully reflect the challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in rural regions or Upper Egypt, where cultural and economic dynamics may differ. Also, the interviews were conducted in Arabic and translated into English. Although great care was taken during translation, some meanings, emotions, or cultural expressions might have been slightly lost or misinterpreted in the process. Lastly, the research also did not include perspectives from external stakeholders like policymakers, banks, or incubator managers. Including their viewpoints might have given a broader understanding of how the environment either helps or limits women's innovation. Even with these limitations, the study still gives an important look at the real-life challenges that many Egyptian women face in their journey to innovate. It lays the groundwork for future research to expand and dive deeper into the same topic.

4.3 Recommendations

This research helped show what challenges women entrepreneurs in Egypt face when trying to be innovative, but it also had its own limitations. So, there are a few things future researchers can do to improve and expand on this study. First, it would be useful to talk to more women

from different places in Egypt not just Cairo. Including women from rural areas or different backgrounds might show more variety in the challenges they face. Also, it would be great to use both interviews and surveys in future research. Interviews are great for understanding feelings and personal stories, but surveys can help measure how common certain challenges are. This way, the results would be easier to compare and apply to more people. Another thing that could help is to spend more time on the research. This would allow for follow-up interviews to see how women's businesses change over time or how they overcome certain challenges. A longer timeline might also allow researchers to explore even more cases in depth. In future research, having more than one person reviewing and analyzing the interviews could make the results fairer and reduce personal bias. It might also help spot patterns that one person might miss. Finally, it would be helpful to also hear from banks, investors, mentors, or policy makers in future studies. Their opinions could help explain what kind of support is missing and what changes are needed to help more women succeed in innovating and growing their businesses.

4.4 Implications

Theoretical implications

This study adds something new to the existing research by showing how both internal and external challenges combine to limit women's ability to innovate in Egypt. Most previous studies tend to focus mainly on external barriers like lack of funding or weak support systems. But what makes this research different is that it also highlights the emotional and psychological side of innovation things like fear of failure, lack of confidence, and the pressure of managing too many roles at once.

Theoretically, this study builds on work from scholars like Cabrera & Mauricio (2017) and Stanković et al. (2023), who explain how confidence and mindset directly influence women's ability to innovate. It supports the idea that internal traits such as self-confidence, risk-taking attitude, and emotional intelligence are just as important as having access to money or networks. But what this study adds is the understanding that these factors don't work in isolation. For example, a woman might have strong family support, but if she lacks confidence or fears social judgment, she may still hesitate to take a risk or try something new.

The research also draws on theories around gendered entrepreneurship, showing how traditional norms and expectations shape how women behave in business. By applying this to the Egyptian context, the study deepens our understanding of how cultural expectations, emotional strain, and gender discrimination intersect with personal challenges to form a bigger, more complex barrier to innovation.

In short, this study expands the theoretical conversation by stressing that innovation isn't just about tools and funding. It's also about how women feel, how they think, and what they go through emotionally. It shows that any serious attempt to support women entrepreneurs must consider not just their access to resources but also their internal battles, emotional resilience, and ability to stay confident under pressure.

Practical Implications

This study doesn't just highlight the challenges it also gives real, practical ideas for how things can improve. One of the biggest lessons I learned from these interviews is that women entrepreneurs need more than just money to succeed. Yes, financial support is important, but it's definitely not enough on its own.

Many of the women said that what they really needed was someone to guide them or simply believe in their ideas. That's why mentorship should be a priority. Programs that connect women with experienced mentors whether other entrepreneurs, business coaches, or industry professionals can make a huge difference. These mentors can offer advice, emotional support, and most importantly, help women feel like they're not alone in their journey.

Confidence building is also key. A lot of the women in this study said they held back at first because they were scared of failing or being judged. That fear stopped them from launching new ideas, even when they had something good. Support programs should include workshops or even simple meetups that focus on building confidence, dealing with stress, and creating safe spaces where women can talk freely without being judged or underestimated.

Another important point is networking. Several women said they didn't know the right people or how to approach suppliers and industry leaders especially in male-dominated fields like manufacturing or logistics. Support programs should teach women how to negotiate, how to

communicate professionally, and how to build strong business relationships that help them grow.

On the policy side, financial access needs to be easier. Many women avoid banks because the process is too complicated or the requirements are too strict. We need more simplified, women-focused funding programs whether through microloans, grants, or partnerships with NGOs. Removing barriers like needing large collateral or endless paperwork could really open doors for women who are just getting started.

Universities and educational institutions also have a big role to play. It's not enough to just teach business plans and marketing. We need courses that focus on mindset, leadership, resilience, and innovation and that are designed to fit the local context. Women in Egypt face different kinds of pressure, especially from family or society, so the content should reflect that and offer practical ways to deal with it.

Even the private sector can help. Big companies can offer mentorship, sponsor competitions for women-led startups, or collaborate with small businesses run by women. These partnerships would give women access to bigger markets, professional networks, and hands-on experience.

In the end, if we want to see more women innovating and leading, we need to give them more than just financial help. We need to create spaces where they feel supported, understood, and empowered to take risks and try new things. That's how we can build a stronger, more inclusive entrepreneurial future in Egypt.

5. Conclusion

This study aimed to understand the key internal and external factors that limit the ability of Egyptian women entrepreneurs to innovate. By conducting 11 in-depth interviews with female founders from various industries, the research offered real-life insights into the barriers they face. The goal was not to generalize, but to deeply explore how these challenges connect and shape women's entrepreneurial journeys.

The findings showed that internal factors like lack of self-confidence, fear of failure, emotional pressure, and family responsibilities often hold women back from trying new ideas. At the same time, external challenges like limited access to finance, social expectations, gender discrimination, and lack of professional networks make it even harder for them to take risks or

grow their businesses. These factors don't happen separately they are often connected, and together, they make it harder for women to innovate freely.

One of the most valuable findings was how emotional intelligence and strong mindset help women push through these challenges. Many participants shared how learning to manage stress, build self-trust, and stay motivated made a real difference in their ability to move forward. This shows that innovation isn't just about money or technology it also depends on how women feel, think, and cope with pressure.

Theoretically, this study adds a deeper layer to the current research by highlighting the emotional and psychological side of innovation. While most existing studies focus on financial or structural challenges, this study shows that internal feelings like fear, stress, or low confidence can also limit innovation just as much as external barriers.

Practically, the results highlight that support programs in Egypt need to go beyond financial help. Women entrepreneurs also need mentorship, emotional support, networking opportunities, and confidence-building spaces. Programs that provide these tools can make a real difference. Policies should also work to make access to finance easier and more inclusive. Lastly, education systems and entrepreneurship programs should include content that focuses on mindset, leadership, and soft skills because these are just as important as business knowledge when it comes to innovation.

In the end, while many challenges still exist, the women in this study showed strength, creativity, and a deep desire to grow. With the right support and a more inclusive environment, they can play a bigger role in shaping Egypt's entrepreneurial future.

Appendix

Interview Questions

General:

1. Can you introduce yourself by sharing your name, age, industry, and how you started your business?
2. Does your company invest in research and development (R&D)? If so, how do you approach R&D to support innovation?

3. Do you think female entrepreneurs in Egypt face more barriers to innovation than men?
If so, what are the key differences?

Innovation Challenges:

4. Can you share an example of an innovative idea you had but struggled to implement?
What challenges did you face, and how did you overcome them?
5. What personal qualities do you think are essential for entrepreneurial success? How have these qualities helped you introduce new ideas or innovations in your business?
6. How does self-confidence influence a woman's ability to take risks and innovate in business? Can you share a personal experience?
7. Have family responsibilities ever made it harder for you to focus on innovation? If so, how did you manage the balance?
8. Have you ever struggled to introduce a new product or service because of fear of failure? What were your main concerns, and how did you overcome them?
9. In your opinion, are Egyptian women more risk-averse in business due to cultural or personal reasons? How does this impact their ability to innovate?

Emotional Intelligence and Mindset:

10. How do you handle stress and pressure in your business? Do you think emotional intelligence helps in fostering innovation?

External Barriers:

11. Have financial limitations ever stopped you from launching a new product or service?
How did you work around this challenge?

12. How have Egypt's cultural and societal norms influenced your ability to innovate and expand your business?

13. Have you experienced gender-based discrimination in business (from investors, customers, or suppliers)? How did this affect your decision-making and innovation efforts?

Networking and Support Systems:

14. How important is networking for business success? Have you faced challenges in accessing professional networks or finding mentors?

Success and Impact:

15. Can you share an example of an innovation you successfully implemented? What impact did it have on your business?

Support and Advice:

16. If you could change one thing to better support women entrepreneurs in Egypt, what would it be and why?

17. What advice would you give to other women in Egypt who want to start a business and introduce new ideas?

Key Barriers to Innovation among Egyptian Women Entrepreneurs

Number of Women (out of 11)

Chart Title

6. References

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